

POTENTIOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF TRIPOSITIVE ANTIMONY WITH ALKALINE HYPOCHLORITE

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A new method has been developed for potentiometric determination of tripositive antimony with alkaline sodium hypochlorite. The titration is satisfactory at elevated temperatures (above 75°) and in presence of a minimum of 3.5% NaOH. Under these conditions, antimony can be determined within an error of less than 1%.

The most commonly used volumetric method for the determination of tripositive antimony is titration with KBrO_3 :

In the conventional method using methyl orange, the end-reaction is slow and often leads to over-titration, particularly if HCl concentration is not sufficient. Belcher (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 3, 578 ; 1951, 5, 30) found that naphthoflavone and quinoline-yellow behaved reversibly and could be used satisfactorily in the above titration.

In the iodine oxidation,

the usually acid solutions are to be neutralised with NaHCO_3 and titration completed immediately after this.

The titration of tripositive antimony with KIO_3 up to the iodine monochloride end-point,

was thoroughly studied by Hammock *et al.* (*Anal. Chem.*, 1948, 20, 1048) who found the titration possible only within a narrow limit of acidity (2.5 - 3.5 N).

In course of an investigation on the dissolution of antimony ore (stibnite) trivalent antimony was observed to be quantitatively oxidised with alkaline hypochlorite solution. A potentiometric method has now been developed for satisfactory and quick determination of trivalent antimony.

The present paper deals with the effects of different variables.

EXPERIMENTAL

N/10 alkaline sodium hypochlorite was prepared by passing chlorine into 0.4N-NaOH (∞), boiled and finally standardised according to Kitchener *et al.* (*Analyst*, 1951, 76, 509).

No suitable indicator could be found for volumetric titration without use of the potentiometer. Use of a known excess of alkali hypochlorite to the alkaline solution

of Sb_2O_3 , and then back-titrating the excess hypochlorite also led to erroneous results, for the obvious reason that Sb^{5+} also took part in the reaction.

Finally the potentiometric method was used. A definite amount of Sb_2O_3 was dissolved in a definite volume (100 c.c.) of 5% NaOH by warming and made to a final volume of 150 c.c. During the titration, the solution was maintained between 80° and 90° and hypochlorite added from a burette. The change in potential was measured in the usual way with a platinum electrode by coupling with a standard calomel electrode. The inflection near the end-point was very clear, being (approx.) 0.05 to 0.10 volt per 0.1 c.c. Experiments were also done with SbCl_3 .

DISCUSSION

Effect of Temperature.—As the ease of solubility of Sb_2O_3 in alkali depends on temperature, possibility of satisfactory titration may be hampered by change (lowering) of temperature. Results of different experiments are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Temp.	Antimony taken.	Antimony found.	Diff.
28°	0.0376 g.	—	—
$50-55^\circ$	0.0376	0.0383 g.	+ 0.7 mg.
$50-55^\circ$	0.0376	0.0382	+ 0.6
$70-75^\circ$	0.0376	0.0375	- 0.1
$80-85^\circ$	0.0376	0.0378	+ 0.2

Erroneously high results are obtained at room temperature. Moreover, the potentiometric curve did not show any clear inflexion point, but changed in a more or less uniform fashion. At $50-55^\circ$, a sharp end-point was obtained from potentiometric reading, but the results were slightly higher. Satisfactory results were obtained at $70-75^\circ$ or higher temperature. But as the end-point is more prominent at $80-85^\circ$, this temperature is recommended for further work.

Effect of Alkali Concentration.—The solubility of Sb_2O_3 in water even at 85° is low. When the Sb_2O_3 was taken in water (instead of alkali) a clear solution was not obtained, and potential change did not show any distinct inflexion point.

Thus, for satisfactory titration, alkali contained in hypochlorite was insufficient and in a series of experiments the Sb_2O_3 was dissolved originally in NaOH having different concentrations.

TABLE II

Temp. = $85^\circ \pm 2.5^\circ$

Conc. of NaOH used for dissolving Sb_2O_3 .	Antimony		Diff.
	taken.	found	
1.0 %	0.0376 g.	0.0430 g.	+ 5.4 mg.
3.0	0.0376	0.0377	+ 0.1
5.0	0.0376	0.0378	+ 0.2
8.0	0.0376	0.0375	- 0.1

Even with an alkali concentration of 1%, except probably for some initial disturbances, the titration was satisfactory, showing a distinct end-point. The result was somewhat higher. With 3.5 % alkali solution, the results were satisfactory, and there was no error in the result even when the alkali concentration was 8%. In fact, in the last experiment, the E. M. F./volume curve was most satisfactory.

Determination of Antimony in varying amounts of Sb₂O₃ and SbCl₃.—After setting the optimum conditions for best titrations, varying proportions of Sb₂O₃ were determined in separate experiments. A comparison has been made of the present method with the KBrO₃ determination (Table III).

TABLE III

Alkali concentration = 5%. Temp. = 85-90°.

Sb taken.	Sb found by potentiometric method (NaOCl)	Diff.	Sb found by KBrO ₃ method.	Diff.
0.0134 g.	0.0135 g.	+ 0.1 mg.	0.0137 g.	+ 0.3 mg.
0.0251	0.0250	- 0.1	0.0253	+ 0.2
0.0376	0.0378	+ 0.2	0.0380	+ 0.4
0.0501	0.0502	+ 0.1	0.0502	+ 0.1
0.0668	0.0666	- 0.2	0.0672	+ 0.4

It will be seen that within the range of our experiments, results of potentiometric titration are quite satisfactory and within 1% error. It may be considered superior to KBrO₃ titration, in which case there is always a positive error (over-titration), and difference relatively wide. This error in KBrO₃ is well known.

TABLE IV

Comparison of results of the titration of SbCl₃ by diff. methods.

Sb found by	SbCl ₃							
	Potentiometric (NaOCl)	...	0.0434	0.0492	0.0578	0.0654	0.0867	0.1054
	KBrO ₃	...	0.0438	0.0496	0.0582	0.0658	0.0868	0.1063
Iodine	...	0.0431	0.0491	0.0577	0.0650	0.0863	0.1049	

In the case of antimony trichloride (Table IV), stock solutions were made by weighing (not accurately, as the material is hygroscopic) different amounts. Aliquot portions from each sample were titrated against NaOCl, and also with KBrO₃ and standard iodine solution.

For hypochlorite titration, the acid solution was neutralised with 5% NaOH, when at first a precipitate was formed which ultimately dissolved in excess alkali on warming. The rest of the titration was as usually found with Sb₂O₃.